

TEACHER

Self-Developed Teacher Education Research Ethics Competency

Education Research Ethics Context Mapping

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Ethics in Education Research: A context mapping report from the TEACH-er project

Final Report

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1. Introduction

Self-Developed Teacher Education Research Ethics Competency (TEACH-er) is an 18-month research project aimed at developing innovative digital resources on Education Research Ethics (ERE) that can be used by teacher-researchers who are not affiliated with any university and thus have limited or no ethics oversight for their classroom-based research.

TEACH-er is funded by European Union (CE-Erasmus + KA2, Small-scale partnerships in school education, KA210-SCH-E91F29BF) led by Dr. Aimie Brennan (Principal Investigator) at Marino Institute of Education, Dublin, Ireland. The team is composed of Dr. Carla Quesada-Pallarès (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain), Mr. Darren Byrne (St Joseph's Post-Primary School, Ireland), Dr. Clíodhna Martin, Dr. John Carroll and Ms. Leah Elsted (Marino Institute of Education, Ireland), MA. Allan-Baez Contreras, Dr. Anna Ciraso-Calí, Dr. Georgeta Ion, and Dr. Angelina Sánchez-Martí (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain).

The project team work with teachers to generate resources to enable teacher-researchers to assess their own skills, knowledge and needs with regards to education research ethics; to build the capacity of teachers to engage in classroom-based research in ways that are ethically sound in the absence of ethical oversight; and to produce resources which will be informed by the real-world unique ethical dilemmas facing teachers-as-researchers.

This report was developed as part of *Activity 2*, which focuses on Education Research Ethics (ERE) Context Mapping, aiming at reviewing relevant scholarly literature, professional ethics oversight in other professions, and ethics policy and guidelines across the EU to generate an in-depth understanding of ERE competence for teacher research. Specifically, the work here presented has been developed by Dr. Carla Quesada-Pallarès, MA. Allan-Baez Contreras and Dr. Georgeta Ion, along with the collaboration of Dr. Anna Ciraso-Calí and Dr. Angelina Sánchez-Martí in the scoping review process, and the contribution of Dr. Aimie Brennan who provided the Irish context and grey literature.

1.1. Our Epistemological Position as a Group

As a group committed to bridging theory and practice, we adopt the stance that every professional requires evidence to inform their actions. In this context, we understand the practitioner-researcher as a professional who actively engages in both practice and research within their field, using inquiry and evidence not only to improve their own practice but also to contribute to broader institutional and educational development (particularly within the classroom and school context).

In line with our thinking, authors such as Griffiths (1985), Goswami and Stillman (1987), and Glesne (1991), consider a **'practitioner-researcher'** as a reflective professional who

systematically investigates their own practice to better understand and improve it. Through this process, they enhance their ability to critically analyse and contextualise situations, reduce impulsive judgments, and make more informed decisions. According to our review of scholarly literature, we can attribute six core characteristics to a practitioner-researcher (see Figure 1). These characteristics are:

- **Critical reflection:** they develop the capacity to critically examine their own actions and the contexts in which they work, leading to deeper understanding and improved practice.
- **Reduced reactivity:** they help lessen the tendency to make quick judgments or to react to situations as they arise. Instead, they promote more thoughtful and deliberate responses.
- **Resourcefulness:** they actively seek out and utilise current research and available resources to inform their practice and decision-making.
- **Contextual awareness:** they are skilled at situating their experiences within broader institutional, social, or educational contexts, allowing for more nuanced interpretations that are relevant to the learners in front of them.
- **Contribution to policy:** their insights and findings can influence policymaking at various levels, from classroom strategies to school-based reforms.
- **Ongoing learning:** they view themselves as lifelong learners, continually evolving through inquiry and evidence-based reflection throughout their careers.

Figure 1. Practitioner-researcher main characteristics. Source: own elaboration.

1.2. Purpose of This Report and Literature Review Procedure

While the term *practitioner-researcher* encompasses a broad range of professionals engaged in systematic reflection on their own practice, this report deliberately narrows its scope to teachers acting as researchers within school settings (primary or post-primary). Our aim is to explore the ethical dimensions that emerge when teachers investigate their own classrooms and use evidence to enhance practice - including how they manage issues of consent, assent, student voice, confidentiality, anonymity, data analysis and reflexivity. By examining these aspects, the report seeks to understand how an ethically informed approach to teacher-led research can strengthen evidence-based decision-making, foster professional growth, and contribute to the development of schools as professional learning communities. For us, education research ethics allows us to focus on both the potential of ethics as a regulatory framework and also as a catalyst for rigorous and innovative practice in education.

To explore how ethics are addressed in school-based teacher research, we carried out a scoping review following the PRISMA guidelines for scoping reviews (Tricco et al., 2018). A scoping review was selected because of its capacity to map a wide and heterogeneous body of literature and to identify key themes and gaps in the field. The search was limited to studies conducted between 2014 and 2025 across three main databases: Scopus, Web of Science (WoS) and Dialnet. Search strings combined common keywords related to ethics, teacher-researchers and classroom-based methodologies. Examples of the search strings and the Boolean queries included:

(ethic* AND action-research AND teach*) OR (ethic* AND "classroom-based research") OR (ethic* AND autoethnography AND teach*) OR (ethic* AND teacher-researcher*) OR (ethic* AND action-research AND teach*) OR (ethic* AND "student voice")

To ensure that we took a comprehensive approach, we used the Spanish equivalents (*éitic**, *maestr**, *docent**, *investigación-acción*, *autoetnografía*, *profesor-investigador*), while explicitly excluding the expression “Higher Education” and other professional domains not school settings related, such as Early Childhood, Initial Teacher Education, Vocational Education and Training, and Adult Education.

The inclusion criteria for this review were deliberately defined to ensure relevance to the scope of our study. Eligible publications were those that (i) reported on teachers conducting research within their own classroom settings; (ii) explicitly addressed ethical dimensions such as dilemmas, reflexivity, consent or related issues; and (iii) were published between 2014 and 2025 in either English or Spanish. Conversely, studies were excluded when they focused exclusively on university or medical contexts, when they were purely theoretical without a clear discussion of ethical aspects, or when they dealt with forms of research unrelated to school-based teaching practice. The voices of teachers as doctoral students were not included, as it was felt that the experience of

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teachers doing PhD research is quite different from those engaging purely in classroom or school-based research.

The initial search retrieved **562 records** from Scopus, WoS and Dialnet. After removing 84 duplicates, **478 records** were screened based on title and abstract. Of these, **80 reports** were selected for full-text assessment against the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Following this process, **31 reports** were excluded for the following reasons:

- i. the study focused exclusively on higher education or medical contexts (n = 18);
- ii. the work lacked an explicit discussion of ethical issues, remaining purely descriptive or theoretical (n = 9); and
- iii. the research was unrelated to classroom-based teaching practice (n = 5).

Ultimately, **39 studies** met the inclusion criteria and were retained for in-depth analysis. Figure 2 shows the PRISMA flow diagram summarising the search and screening process.

From the final set of studies, data were systematically extracted with a focus on three main areas: (1) the research design and context in which the studies were conducted (for instance, action research, participatory inquiry or autoethnography); (2) the ethical dimensions explicitly addressed in each work (such as informed consent, protection and inclusion of students' voices, confidentiality, and reflexivity); and, (3) more broadly, how these elements contribute to understanding the formation of the teacher-researcher identity and the centrality of ethical competence in educational research.

Alongside academic publications (Figure 2), the review examined a selection of **43 grey literature resources**, including guidelines, networks, policy statements and international frameworks specifically related to research ethics. While few of these documents targeted school-based teacher-research, many offered transferable principles relevant to ethical decision-making within educational contexts.

After applying the exclusion criteria, **20 documents** were retained for analysis. Resources were excluded when they were not education-focused (n=4), lacked practical applicability (n=8), or were not aligned with the research aim (n=12). The remaining documents were those that provided relevant, adaptable guidance to support ethical teacher-led inquiry and complemented the academic literature by offering broader perspectives and practical frameworks often absent from peer-reviewed studies.

Figure 2. PRISMA Protocol used for ERE Context Mapping¹. Source: Own elaboration.

Key sources from the grey literature include:

- Professional ethical guidelines (e.g., BERA, 2024; AERA, 2011; EERA, 2025; SSRI, 2010).
- Research integrity networks and frameworks (e.g., ENRIO, 2025; UKRIO, 2024; EUREC, n.d.; Irish University Association, 2024; ENERI, 2016; Markukula Center, 2025).
- Policy statements and legal frameworks (e.g., Spain's Law 14/2011; Ireland's National Policy Statement, 2024; the Common Rule, 1991; Declaration of Helsinki, 1964; Ethics Committees).

¹The information of documents reviewed included in this Scoping Review can be found in the Excel file attached to this publication. The TEACH-er PRISMA grey literature review data base is available from: DOI [10.5281/zenodo.18302176](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18302176) the PRISMA Protocol is available here: DOI [10.5281/zenodo.18302359](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18302359)

- Practical tools and initiatives promoting ethics awareness (e.g., Open Ethics 2021; Toolkit on Teacher Codes of Conduct, 2009; ETHICS Project, 2023; IRRESISTIBLE Project, n.d.; The Lab: Avoiding Misconduct, 2023).

Although most were originated from academic, biomedical, or international research settings, they provide relevant insights that can be adapted to support ethical teacher-led inquiry. This grey literature complements the academic review by offering broader perspectives and practical resources often absent from peer-reviewed studies.

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2. Understanding the Concept of the Teacher-Researcher

Traditionally, the role of a teacher was predominantly about subject didacts or the transmission of knowledge. As the expert, guided by curriculum, they transferred their knowledge to the learner using various pedagogical approaches. In more recent education policy, there has been a notable shift toward positioning the teacher as a professional who is always interpreting, adapting and sharing knowledge in ways that adapt to complex societal and professional demands with creativity, criticality, and resilience.

It was a decade ago when the *European Network on Teacher Education Policies (ENTEP)* signalled a shift in the teaching profession toward a more dynamic, reflective, and research-oriented model (Schratz, Pecek & Lucu, 2014). This new model envisions teachers as multifaceted professionals: capable of adapting to diverse contexts, using and generating knowledge, and making informed decisions to improve student learning and school experiences. This aligns closely with the 2021 UNESCO report, which conceptualizes teachers as “reflexive practitioners and knowledge producers, they contribute to growing bodies of knowledge needed to transform educational environments, policies, research, and practice, within and beyond their own profession” (UNESCO, 2021, p.85), actively contributing to the transformation of educational environments, policies, and practices.

Recent publications by Kilbrink et al. (2026), Hudson (2022) and Craig (2010) have emphasised the position of teachers as research informed curriculum makers. This work has both acknowledged and awarded teachers more latitude to use their professional judgement and discretion in their daily work. It also highlights the need for teachers to be open to and engaged in continuous professional development (and/or education research) to ensure that they are up to date on all aspects of selecting content, materials and pedagogical tools required for the learners within their context.

2.1. The Teacher’s Profession as an Inquiry-Led Practice

For many scholars, the shift towards teachers as active agents, curriculum makers and professionals has led to the requirement for engagement in inquiry, research and data-informed practice. This vision shifts the role of the teacher from knowledge consumer to knowledge producer: an agent of innovation who systematically investigates their own teaching (Böttcher-Oschmann, Groß Ophoff & Thiel, 2021).

The concept ‘**teacher as researcher**’, understood as similar to the term ‘practitioner-researcher’, encapsulates this shift. It defines educators as inquiry-minded professionals who critically reflect on their practice, adopt research-informed strategies, and generate context-specific knowledge to enhance learning. Rather than being passive implementers of externally produced knowledge, teacher-researchers engage in classroom-based investigations using tools adapted from empirical research, often rooted in qualitative, action-based, or participatory paradigms. They interpret and

enact curriculum based on their classroom contexts, and the evidence they generate through research.

From an historical point of view, the notion of the *teacher as researcher* has a rich lineage in educational theory, rooted in the mid-twentieth century. Lawrence Stenhouse is often credited with popularizing the idea in the United Kingdom in the 1960s arguing that teachers should not simply implement a curriculum designed elsewhere but should take an active, investigative stance toward their practice.

Drawing on the seminal work of Stenhouse (1975), the concept of the *teacher as researcher* emphasises the idea that teachers are active agents in their professional development and in the development of curriculum through reflective inquiry. According to Stenhouse, teachers are not merely implementers of predefined curricula but are engaged in ongoing, systematic investigation of their practice to improve student learning and adapt content to their specific contexts. This view positions teachers as reflective practitioners who use research as a tool for continuous professional growth, emphasising the importance of their interpretive and exploratory roles rather than strictly formal scientific investigation.

In this framework, the teacher-researcher is seen as someone who:

- Engages in reflective inquiry about their teaching and student responses.
- Uses data from their classroom to inform practice.
- Contributes to curriculum development through these insights.
- Sees themselves as both practitioners and investigators, bridging theory and practice.

Stenhouse (1975) proposes that teachers develop a “research stance” to examine what happens in their own classrooms, to test hypotheses, to reflect, to revise, and thereby to contribute to curriculum development. Over time this idea expanded into what later came to be known as action research or practitioner research, with teachers engaging in systematic enquiry into their own instructional practices, curricula, and pupils (Elliott and Norris, 2012).

Cochran-Smith and Lytle (1993) further refined the concept, in which they distinguish different ways of thinking about teacher knowledge and teacher learning. For example, they contrast “knowledge for practice” (where university researchers generate knowledge to be consumed by teachers) with “knowledge in practice” (embedded in experienced teacher’s actions) and “knowledge of practice” (where teachers do systematic inquiry into teaching, curriculum, learners, etc., generating knowledge themselves) to challenge the traditional hierarchy between academic researchers and teachers (Leena, 1996). Their later work (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 2015) elaborated how inquiry becomes not just a project or method but a professional posture where teachers continually ask questions, investigate, reflect, learn, in community, and use those investigations to transform policy, practice, and their own identity as educators.

A more critical perspective was adopted by Hammersley (1993), who sketched the development of the idea and interrogates its claims. He acknowledges that teacher research can make education more relevant and democratically grounded, but he also raises doubts: about the feasibility (time, resources), about whether teacher research can meet the standards of methodological rigor, and whether it can or should replace “traditional” research by university-based scholars. Over decades this has changed professional development, teacher education, and research methodologies so that many systems now recognise teacher inquiry, collaborative research, and reflective practice as legitimate and important.

Teacher-researchers now draw on existing research and resources to support their analysis, contributing to more thoughtful and evidence-based policymaking within their institutions. As la Velle (2024) argues, this reflective, iterative model - understanding, preparing, instructing, assessing, and reflecting - underpins quality teacher education. Research engagement fosters teacher identity, supports inclusion, enhances digital competence, and develops professional resilience. It empowers teachers to navigate complexity in diverse educational contexts and promote equity in increasingly diverse classrooms.

2.2. Theoretical Foundations and Empirical Insights

The foundations of teacher-researcher practice are well established. Foster and Nixon (1978) argue that the traditional divide between teaching and research is both outdated and unproductive. Teaching itself is inherently a process of disciplined inquiry, and teachers are well-positioned to engage in reflective, practice-based research. They advocate equipping teachers with research methods drawn from the social sciences (e.g. philosophy, sociology, psychology) and supporting collaboration between teachers and academic researchers. Action research, evaluation, and triangulation are emphasized as especially useful for bridging theory and practice.

Similarly, Alexakos (2015) asserts that teachers possess unique experiential insights that are often absent in traditional academic research. They promote authentic inquiry within the classroom, grounded in reflective practice, action research, and practitioner inquiry. This approach not only enhances teachers' agency but rebalances the research-practice divide, allowing teachers to contribute meaningfully to educational theory and reform. Alexakos further criticizes research conducted ‘from the outside’, noting its frequent disconnection from classroom realities. Instead, he calls for participatory, teacher-led research that is context-rich and professionally fulfilling, positioning inquiry as central to both personal and systemic growth in education.

To become highly effective professionals capable of continuously updating their knowledge to meet the evolving needs of their students, making informed decisions, and contributing to the body of knowledge, teachers must actively engage with and participate in research (Banegas & Consoli, 2025). This objective transforms teachers into professionals who not only acquire knowledge but also generate it. It positions them

as individuals capable of inquiry regarding their teaching methods, adept at utilizing diverse sources of data to inform their practice and ultimately empowered to investigate and enhance their own teaching strategies (Böttcher-Oschmann et al., 2021). Research literacy has been established as a broad view on the function of research-based teacher education and is defined as "the ability to judiciously use, apply, and develop research as an intrinsic component of one's teaching" (Evans et al., 2017, p.404). The goal is for teachers to not only be knowledgeable research consumers but also to be able to conduct their own research to examine treatments and educational methods (Menter & Flores, 2021).

While possessing research competence in professional practice has numerous advantages for professional development and, ultimately, for students' learning outcomes, teacher education programmes on a global scale have encountered criticism for their excessive emphasis on theory, disconnection from practical classroom application, or the absence of opportunities for students to cultivate robust research-related skills during initial teacher education (Afdal, 2017). This ultimately is associated with pre-service teachers being short of what has been called 'research capacity' (Oancea et al., 2021). Skills such as interpreting research findings, engaging in practitioner-based research, and searching literature have been especially highlighted (Gleeson et al., 2017) as essential for developing teacher researchers.

The acquisition of such knowledge and skills can be facilitated through teacher education programmes grounded in research, which have the potential to better equip future teachers to navigate and enhance their multifaceted roles as professional educators (Poulton, 2023). However, the integration of research into teaching is not straightforward and requires teacher educators to explicitly convey the presence of research within their teaching in a manner that is both evident and accessible to students (Wang & Newton, 2025).

2.3. Benefits of Research Engagement for Teachers

Engaging in research offers multiple benefits for teachers' professional development. Research has been shown to:

- Foster deeper subject-matter understanding and pedagogical awareness (Turner, Wuetherick, & Healey, 2008).
- Enhance motivation for postgraduate education and continuous learning (Ion & Iucu, 2016).
- Increase awareness of personal learning processes (Todd, Bannister, & Clegg, 2004).
- Enable critical engagement with the work of others (Reis-Jorge, 2005).
- Stimulate professional autonomy and self-efficacy (Impedovo & Khatoun Malik, 2016).

These findings are echoed in the concept of **research literacy**, which refers to the ability to judiciously use, apply, and produce research as part of one's teaching (Evans, Waring, & Christodoulou, 2017). However, as Brooks (2021) notes, many pre-service teachers lack research capacity: skills like interpreting findings, conducting practitioner inquiry, and critically engaging with academic literature. Strengthening initial teacher education (ITE) programmes through authentic, embedded research experiences can better prepare future teachers for their multifaceted roles and support lifelong learning.

The need to develop **ethical competence within teacher education** emerges as a central concern for the quality and legitimacy of both educational practice and research. As Honan (2007) asserts, the quality of practitioner research rests upon the quality of the ethical dimensions that are understood and emphasised. This recognition positions ethics not as a peripheral consideration but as a foundational element of professional practice and inquiry. Teacher education, therefore, must ensure that future professionals are not only equipped with methodological and pedagogical skills but also prepared to engage critically and responsibly with the ethical dimensions of their work.

It is also important to recognise that the emphasis on research literacy within initial teacher education is a relatively recent development. Consequently, many practising teachers who graduated from ITE programmes within the past decade may not have been provided with formal instruction in research methods, practitioner research, or research ethics. Despite this, these teachers are expected to engage in, and routinely do engage with, educational research within their school contexts.

In Ireland, new policies such as Looking at Our Schools in 2022 and 2024 (Department of Education Inspectorate, 2022a) provide a data driven quality framework for whole school improvement, requiring teachers to work with data to inform school policy. The Teaching Council of Ireland provides funding to teachers through a Research Bursary Scheme (RBS) (2026) which supports teachers who are wishing to carry out new research; and the Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools (DEIS) Action Plan (Department of Education Inspectorate, 2022b) outlines the Department of Education's vision to guide policy through data-informed decision which requires teachers and schools to annual review data they have generated in relation to targets set by the school. Teachers work in generating, analysing and applying data must be recognised as on-going teacher research and should be underpinned by basic research literacy and ethical research practice.

In Catalonia, recent public policies have similarly elevated the role of data-informed teacher research within school improvement. The *Pla de Recerca Educativa de Catalunya* (Research Education Plan in Catalonia), developed by the Servei de Recerca Educativa and the Departaments d'Educació and Recerca i Universitats (2023), established a strategic framework that emphasized: working systematically with school-generated data; promoting funding mechanisms for research directly involving educators; and ensuring that scientific evidence is transferred into both classroom

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practice and educational policy. Notably, the RecercAULA (Servei de Recerca Educativa, 2023) programme, emerging from this plan, offered grants and fostered networks of teacher–researchers and research-active schools, thereby encouraging annual data reviews to monitor progress against targets set by individual schools. Activities and training programmes related to generating, analysing, and applying data were framed explicitly as continual forms of teacher-led research, and are anchored in expectations of fundamental research literacy and adherence to ethical research standards.

Ethical practice in research, and particularly in school-based research, can be characterised by competing demands: the need to ensure quality and rigour, to situate the work within a participatory and democratic frame, to acknowledge that one is working within a system of morality and professional standards, and to manage the challenges of objectivity, access, and informed consent in the workplace, all while maintaining a commitment to improving educational practice in a genuine way. These tensions underscore the complexity of ethical engagement in educational contexts and the need for professionals who can balance moral reasoning with research integrity and practical judgment.

Ethical competence thus encompasses more than adherence to institutional codes or procedural compliance. It involves the cultivation of moral sensitivity, ethical reasoning, and reflective judgment—capacities that enable teachers to identify, analyse, and respond appropriately to the complex ethical dilemmas that arise in educational settings. Such competence requires an awareness of the values and assumptions underlying pedagogical and policy decisions, as well as a commitment to act with integrity, fairness, and respect for all learners. Within this framework, ethics is conceived not as an external constraint but as an intrinsic dimension of professional identity and agency.

From an evidence-informed perspective, ethical competence is also a precondition for ensuring the quality, trustworthiness, and transparency of educational research and practice. Gorard and Taylor (2004) argue that quality is “paramount,” since unethical practices inevitably undermine the credibility and reliability of findings. Similarly, Furlong and Oancea’s (2005) *Quality Framework* highlights trustworthiness and explicitness as essential sub-dimensions of rigorous inquiry. In this sense, ethical competence strengthens not only the moral integrity of practitioners but also the epistemic validity of their professional actions and research endeavours.

Ethical practice in education extends beyond individual responsibility to encompass broader commitments to **social justice, equality, and participatory democracy** (Griffiths, 1998). Teacher education, therefore, has an obligation to prepare teachers who can critically engage with the social, cultural, and political contexts of their work. Developing ethical competence implies recognising the moral purposes of education -

questioning whose interests are served, whose voices are marginalised, and how educational practices can contribute to more equitable and inclusive outcomes.

Integrating research into teaching is not a simple matter of adding coursework. As Wang and Newton (2024) argue, it requires academics and educators to **explicitly and visibly embed research within their teaching practice**, demonstrating its value and relevance in accessible ways. When research is deeply woven into the learning experiences of pre-service and in-service teachers, it promotes reflective professionalism and the capacity to navigate complexity and uncertainty. In their scoping review, Xiao and Quesada-Pallarès (2025, p.142) state that “studies emphasized that institutional structure, school culture and professional community play a key role in the construction of TRI [teacher-researcher identity]. When teachers are supported by time, resources, peer collaboration and recognition mechanisms, their research capabilities and identity will be significantly enhanced (Finney & Laurence, 2017; Mills et al., 2025)”.

In this context, teachers become agents of transformation: able not only to respond to change, but to drive it. Their inquiries contribute not only to their own development but to collective professional knowledge and school improvement.

2.4. Challenges and Tensions in Teacher-Led Research

Being a teacher-researcher also implies some tensions. Mercer (2007) characterised the teacher-researcher as an *insider*, someone who possesses lived familiarity with the context under research -whether through biographical attributes (such as gender, culture, or professional role) or through direct participation in the institutional life of the setting. Indeed, the teacher-researcher: (i) shares the same professional environment as the individuals being studied; (ii) has knowledge of the internal dynamics, power relations, routines, and unwritten codes of the institution; and (iii) may have pre-existing relationships with participants, which can influence access, trust, and the interpretation of data.

Mercer (2007) further clarified that this role is not fixed; rather, it fluctuates depending on the topic, timing, location, and the individuals involved. Thus, a teacher-researcher may feel more like an insider in certain situations (e.g., when interviewing fellow teachers) and more like an outsider in others (e.g., when engaging with members of the management team).

On the other hand, and despite the value of research engagement, teachers face significant challenges when acting as researchers, which can limit the effectiveness and sustainability of their inquiry. Authors such as Hammersley (1993), Afdal (2017), and Mahat and Bradbeer (2024) identify eight challenges when teachers act as researchers:

1. **Uncertainty of Outcomes:** Reflective inquiry does not always yield clear or applicable solutions. Research may not result in outcomes superior to traditional practices, leading to frustration or disillusionment.

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2. **Opportunity Costs:** Conducting research demands time and effort that could otherwise be dedicated to planning, teaching, or student support. Teachers must weigh the benefits of inquiry against competing priorities.
3. **Potential for Misconceptions:** Teachers situated perspectives may limit objectivity, and without access to diverse information sources or formal methodological training, their conclusions might lack broader validity or applicability.
4. **Contextual Complexity:** The inherent variability of classroom contexts often undermines the generalizability of findings, making it difficult to extract transferable principles.
5. **Role Contradictions:** Teachers may experience tension between their traditional roles and the role of researcher, particularly when inquiry challenges established norms or hierarchies in the classroom.
6. **Professional Identity Tensions:** Engaging in research may unintentionally highlight the lower status historically assigned to the teaching profession, raising questions about authority, legitimacy, and recognition.
7. **Misapplication of Research Standards:** Applying academic standards of rigor and validity to classroom research may be inappropriate, risking confusion or discouragement among practitioner-researchers.
8. **External Constraints:** Institutional policies, access restrictions, or bureaucratic hurdles may inhibit teachers' capacity to conduct or publish their research effectively.

3. Becoming a teacher-researcher: competences and ethics

The 21st-century education landscape mirrors a society undergoing deep social, technological, methodological, and ideological change. These transformations bring new expectations not only for educational systems, but also for how we prepare teachers to become professionals capable of responding to complexity (Pedrero-García, Fernández, & Crespo, 2017).

In this context, teacher education is increasingly expected to cultivate not only technical skills, but also a research-oriented mindset and an ethical sensitivity that enable professionals to generate and use knowledge as part of their practice (Bona, 2016). According to Mercer (2007) the *insider* research offers distinct advantages -such as easier access, deeper contextual understanding, and stronger rapport- but also entails significant ethical and methodological challenges.

3.1. Research Competence within the Teacher-Researcher Identity

Research competence refers to the combination of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and dispositions necessary to conduct rigorous inquiry (Ravelo Peña et al., 2019). This competence allows teachers to analyse their practice, make informed decisions, and contribute to the professional knowledge base of education.

Developing research competence involves a set of interrelated capabilities that go beyond technical skills (Hernández-Escorcia et al., 2025). It requires the ability to formulate research questions that are both relevant and sensitive to the educational context, to ground inquiries in solid theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence, and to select and apply research methods that are appropriate to the nature of the problem. Equally important is the capacity to interpret results critically, drawing meaningful conclusions that inform practice, and to communicate findings in ways that contribute to personal growth as well as to institutional and collective development (Colen & Castro, 2017; Ayuste González, & Payà, 2024).

Underpinning all these dimensions is a continuous process of reflection on one's own role as a teacher-researcher: a reflexivity that makes it possible to navigate the tensions between teaching and research. Within this methodological competence, **ethical responsibility** occupies a central place, ensuring that every stage of the research process is guided by respect, care, and integrity (Contreras, 2025).

Thus, ethical competence constitutes a core dimension of research competence, extending far beyond mere procedural compliance. It entails a relational and situated understanding of ethics (Gibbs & Costley, 2006), in which teacher-researchers are called to embed ethical considerations throughout all phases of the research process, from the formulation of questions to data collection, analysis, and dissemination of findings. This comprehensive perspective implies safeguarding the dignity and rights of participants,

guaranteeing confidentiality and informed consent, preventing harm, fostering equity and inclusion, and acknowledging the power dynamics inherent in insider research.

Recent research underscores that the development of a teacher-researcher identity is not a static acquisition of skills, but rather a dynamic and situated process shaped by reflection, agency and collaboration. This identity emerges at the intersection of teaching and research, requiring teachers to negotiate their dual role, gradually shifting from consumers of knowledge to active co-constructors of contextually relevant evidence (Xiao & Quesada-Pallarès, 2025). The literature further shows that the formation of this identity is strengthened by reflective practice, action research and engagement in professional learning communities, while also challenged by tensions such as role conflict, institutional constraints and emotional demands.

3.2. Ethical Practices Across the Research Cycle

The literature identifies a wide range of concrete practices through which ethical competence becomes visible in teacher-led research (see Figure 3). Nic Mhuirí et al. (2025) mapped ethical principles from professional codes to research practices, proposing school-level protocols to guide decision-making in collaborative reflection.

At the **design stage**, ethical competence is reflected in a deliberate effort to ground inquiries in previous evidence and to adopt rigorous, coherent and transparent methods (ALLEA, 2023). This stage also involves collaboration and democratic values, such as creating peer support networks, communities of practice and co-planning spaces (Quiroga & Cortés, 2024).

Teacher-researchers are called to reflect on their positionality, biases and possible conflicts of interest, acknowledging how their dual role may influence the process and findings (Agard et al., 2019). When needed, they are encouraged to seek ethical advice or review through institutional or professional networks (Bertram et al., 2024).

Regarding **responsibilities towards participants**, ethical competence involves designing research that is inclusive, equitable and non-harmful. This includes paying attention to the voices of under-represented groups (Save the Children, 2004), anticipating the potential impact of participation (Faldet & Nes, 2024) and establishing protocols to manage risk and protection when sensitive disclosures emerge (UKRIO, 2024).

Mercer (2007) reflected on the fact that *insiders* may face bias due to pre-existing relationships and perceived alignments. Informants might tailor their responses based on what they believe the researcher wants to hear, especially if the researcher has previously expressed strong views on the topic.

Central to this dimension is the design of processes for informed and ongoing consent, adapted to the age and circumstances of participants, ensuring that autonomy and

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agency are respected throughout (Rogers, Labadie, & Pole, 2016; Bakerson et al., 2015). Consent practices are complemented by clear communication, attention to cultural and linguistic diversity, and recognition of the right to withdraw at any moment.

Figure 3. Ethics Research Competence in Teacher-Researcher. Source: Adapted from Contreras (2025).

In the data collection phase, teacher-researchers must ensure confidentiality and secure data management while also promoting meaningful and authentic participation. Strategies include multimodal and participatory approaches that allow students, families and colleagues to express themselves in their own terms (Finefer-Rosenbluh, 2022; Busher, 2022). This phase also demands careful judgment when balancing confidentiality with a duty of care in cases of risk or harm (Finefer-Rosenbluh, 2022). Furthermore, as highlighted by the UKRIO (2024) and Agard et al. (2019), data not originally collected for research, such as administrative or institutional records, should only be reused or linked with research data when explicit informed consent has been obtained from participants.

Beyond these technical aspects, this stage raises complex ethical dilemmas when teachers have access to sensitive information by virtue of their professional role such as academic records, personal or family data- that was not originally collected for research

purposes. The ethical use of such existing data requires explicit reflection and, where appropriate, renewed consent from participants, in line with current guidelines (UKRIO, 2024).

The dual position of teacher and researcher also brings to the surface questions about **role boundaries**: deciding when one is acting as a teacher and when as a researcher, and how to prevent this overlap from undermining trust. Power dynamics are particularly relevant here, as the teacher's authority in the classroom can affect the voluntariness of participation and the authenticity of responses. For example, *insider researchers* often engage in reciprocal dialogue, sharing personal experiences to build rapport (Mercer, 2007). While this can foster trust and richer data, it risks leading informants or contaminating the data.

This is why the literature recommends combining clear consent protocols with ongoing reflexivity, often supported through reflective journals, to critically examine how positionality and insider knowledge may shape what data are collected, how they are interpreted, and the balance between confidentiality and a duty of care in cases of risk or harm (Agard et al., 2019). The *EECERA Ethical Code for Early Childhood Researchers* (Bertram et al., 2024) reinforces these principles by framing consent as a continuous and negotiated process and by highlighting the need to reflect on power relations and the researcher's ethical responsibility to protect participants through ongoing reflexive practice.

Conducting insider research entails navigating a particularly intricate ethical landscape, especially in relation to informed consent, the safeguarding of confidentiality, and the dissemination of findings. Mercer (2007) illustrated this complexity through her decision to refrain from validating interview transcripts with participants or sharing her research outcomes within the institutions studied. This approach was adopted to preserve participant anonymity and to mitigate potential professional risks.

During **analysis and dissemination**, ethical practice is expressed through fair representation and methodological transparency, avoiding stereotypes or misinterpretations of marginalized groups (Agard et al., 2019). The literature also highlights the value of co-interpreting results with participants (Bourke et al., 2017) and returning findings to the communities involved, as well as discussing authorship and recognizing contributions (Areljung et al., 2021).

Moreover, the ethical implications of using incidental data -such as information obtained through overheard conversations- are also addressed by Mercer (2007). While such data may offer valuable insights, she emphasizes that its inclusion in research must be ethically justified and must not compromise the trust established between the teacher-researcher and participants. In this regard, the insider researcher must exercise

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heightened sensitivity and discretion, ensuring that the boundaries between legitimate inquiry and ethical transgression remain clearly defined.

Dissemination practices should prioritise the educational and social value of research for participants and the wider community over purely academic objectives, ensuring that knowledge contributes to collective growth (Wisener et al., 2025).

Taken together, these practices show that ethical competence is not limited to consent and confidentiality: it also encompasses scientific integrity, collaboration, inclusion, reflexivity, risk management, transparent dissemination, and social usefulness. Through these intertwined dimensions, teacher-researchers become agents of transformation, producing contextually relevant, evidence informed and ethically grounded knowledge.

4. Spaces of Intervention for the Teacher-Researcher

Exploring the types of research conducted by teacher-researchers and the contexts in which they operate reveals that integrating research into teaching goes far beyond simply adding academic content. As Wang and Newton (2025) emphasise, it entails a deliberate and visible embedding of inquiry within educational practice (or school placement stages in initial education), shaped by the specific environments, both within and beyond the classroom, where such research takes place.

This scoping review has revealed a clear trend in the research methodologies employed by teacher-researchers and the contexts in which they are applied. Broadly, four methodological orientations emerge. **(Participatory) Action Research** is frequently used in both early childhood and secondary education, often addressing ethical, social, or environmental issues (e.g., Rogers et al., 2016). This approach is inherently ethical in nature, as it involves collaboration with participants and requires ongoing negotiation of consent, voice, and power dynamics.

Qualitative Case Studies are applied in classroom settings to explore pedagogical innovations or student engagement (e.g., Makar et al., 2024). These studies often incorporate ethical considerations related to student privacy, informed consent, and the researcher's dual role as educator. **Narrative Inquiry and Reflexive Methods** are used to examine teacher identity, ethics, and professional development (e.g., Song, 2017). These approaches place ethics at the core of the research process, as they demand transparency, vulnerability, and critical self-reflection from the researcher.

Finally, **Theoretical and Reflective Approaches** are employed to conceptualize teacher-researcher roles and ethical frameworks (e.g., Tan, 2017), offering normative insights into how educators can engage ethically with their practice and research.

Across all these methodological orientations, ethics emerge not as a peripheral concern but as a foundational principle. Whether through collaborative engagement, personal narrative, or theoretical reflection, teacher-researchers are called to navigate complex ethical landscapes that demand attentiveness to context, relationships, and the moral implications of their work. This literature underscores the importance of ethics as both a guiding framework and a lived practice in educational research.

4.1. Typologies of Research Conducted by Teacher-Researchers

A deeper analysis of the studies allowed the identification of the most common research methodologies used by teachers-researchers (see Table 1). It is important to consider that most of the studies reviewed used more than one methodology, which is common in a paradigm towards social's transformation. This is why the total number of occurrences is higher than the studies included in the scoping review.

Table 1. Most Common Research Methodologies used by Teachers-Researchers.

Methodology	Occurrences
Participatory Action Research	13
Action Research	11
Student Voice Research	8
Practitioner Inquiry or Practitioner Research	6
Autoethnography or Personal Narrative	5
(Classroom) Case Study	3

Participatory Action Research (PAR) is the most common research methodology found in the scoping review. It is conceived as a collaborative research methodology that involves participants as co-researchers in all stages of the inquiry process. It seeks to democratize knowledge production, foster critical reflection, and promote social change by engaging communities in identifying issues and implementing solutions. Thus, participants are not only the source of information of the researcher, but they are part of the research process, contributing sometimes to the same extent as the researcher.

PAR key characteristics are:

- Emphasizes co-creation of knowledge
- Rooted in social justice and empowerment
- Integrates education, reflection, and action
- Often used in marginalized or vulnerable communities

In the literature review, 13 studies regarding PAR were found. The selected articles collectively illustrate how PAR serves as a transformative and ethically grounded methodology in educational contexts. Across these studies, ethical considerations are central: researchers grapple with issues of voice, consent, power dynamics, and cultural sensitivity. Whether working with young children, marginalized communities, or in decolonial settings, PAR is framed as a relational, reflexive process that prioritizes inclusion, agency, and contextually responsive inquiry.

Ethics in PAR are not procedural but deeply embedded in practice and relationships, enacted through ongoing dialogue, mutual respect, and a commitment to equity and

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inclusion (e.g., Clough & Tarr, 2021; Mitra & McCormick, 2017; Serpa Perdomo, 2024; Wagle et al., 2023; Seehawer, 2018). It is inseparable from the methodology's core values of participation, empowerment, and social transformation. Specifically, these studies use PAR alongside relational ethics, which is evident in how researchers co-design inquiries with participants (e.g., Agard et al., 2019; Stapleton et al., 2017), support youth agency while safeguarding well-being (Mitra & McCormick, 2017), and prioritize care and responsiveness in classroom-based research (Edwards-Groves & Davidson, 2020). For instance, Clough and Tarr (2021) implemented iterative consent processes and reflexive products to safeguard young participants in arts-based interventions. Indeed, these studies show that ethical research in PAR is not just about doing no harm, but about cultivating relationships that are respectful, empowering, and transformative.

Serpa Perdomo's decolonial approach PAR (2024) highlighted the conflicts between institutional expectations and community realities, especially in under-resourced or politically complex contexts. To overcome this, Serpa Perdomo grounded research on local praxis and collective reflection. Stapleton et al. (2017) demonstrate how PAR empowers veteran teachers to co-lead inquiries into food justice, emphasizing relational ethics and the value of insider expertise. Thus, there is a concern for ethical engagement with vulnerable populations, echoed in Rogers et al. (2016) and Burroughs (2018), who explore how to balance protection and participation in early childhood research.

Wagle et al. (2023) emphasise ethical engagement through relational ontology, where trust and shared understanding evolve among diverse stakeholders. Like other PAR studies, it highlights ethics as a dynamic, context-sensitive process involving informed consent, power negotiation, and collective reflection.

Other studies, such as Areljung et al. (2021) and Alasiry (2019), explore how ethical considerations emerge in the distribution of ownership and the inclusion of marginalized voices. These works show that ethical practice in PAR involves negotiating roles, responsibilities, and power dynamics throughout the research process. Bourke et al. (2017) and Seehawer (2018) emphasize the importance of culturally responsive and decolonial ethics. They advocate for reflexivity, the integration of local knowledge, and community-rooted methodologies, positioning ethics as a dynamic, situated, and relational process.

Action Research (AR) is the second most common research methodology. It is a reflective, iterative process of inquiry conducted by teachers within their own professional contexts to improve practices, understand phenomena, and generate knowledge through cycles of planning, acting, observing, and reflecting. It originated by Kurt Lewin in the 1940s, emphasizing democratic participation, collaboration, and the integration of theory and practice.

Its main characteristics present AR as:

- Conducted by practitioners in their own settings

- Aiming at solving real-world problems
- Involving cycles of inquiry and reflection
- Encouraging collaboration and empowerment

The scoping review conducted revealed that 11 articles used AR as a research methodology (e.g. Andrew, 2017; Bakerson et al., 2015; Bergmark, 2020; Bergmark et al., 2024; Mueller et al., 2023; Tan, 2017), particularly when teachers seek to improve their own practices through collaborative, reflective, and ethically grounded inquiry. The articles illustrate diverse applications of AR, ranging from inclusive education to professional development, each contributing unique insights into the dynamics of teacher-researcher engagement.

Ethics within AR are deeply embedded in its participatory, reflective, and context-sensitive nature. Across the reviewed literature, ethics is not treated as a procedural add-on but as a foundational element guiding every stage of the research process. Scholars such as Gibbs and Costley (2006), Bergmark (2020) and Bergmark et al. (2024) emphasize an **ethics of care**, where mutual responsibility, relational sensitivity, and contextual awareness shape the researcher-participant dynamic. This is particularly relevant in practitioner or insider research, where dual roles can create ethical tensions, as highlighted by Bakerson et al. (2015) in their discussion of Institutional Review Board challenges.

AR empowers educators to become agents of change, as seen in Andrew (2017), Niemi (2019), and Serra et al. (2023), but this empowerment comes with ethical obligations—toward students, colleagues, and the integrity of the research process. In inclusive and participatory contexts, such as those described by Alasiry (2019) and Hopman (2021), ethics involves ensuring meaningful participation, safeguarding agency, and navigating emotional and relational complexities. Similarly, in Mueller et al. (2023), ethical practice requires attentiveness to power dynamics, voice, and representation.

Ultimately, ethics in AR is enacted through iterative cycles of reflection and action, where researchers continuously negotiate their responsibilities in relation to others. It is a lived, dialogic process that aligns with the democratic and transformative aims of AR itself.

Student Voice Research has emerged as a critical methodological and ethical orientation in educational inquiry, foregrounding the perspectives, experiences, and agency of students in shaping their learning environments. It explores how students express their perspectives, participate in decision-making, and influence educational practices. It is rooted in democratic and ethical principles that recognize students as competent social agents.

Student Voice research:

- Centres on students' perspectives and agency

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- Often uses participatory and inclusive methods
- Addresses issues of equity, inclusion, and power
- Can involve tools like photovoice, interviews, and surveys

The eight studies identified in this review (e.g., Faldet & Nes, 2024; Mannion et al., 2024; Rogers et al., 2016; Finefter-Rosenbluh, 2022; O'Neill, 2018; Quiroga & Cortés, 2024) demonstrate a range of methodological approaches -participatory action research, narrative inquiry, photovoice, and practitioner enquiry- all unified by a commitment to ethical engagement with student participants. These studies grapple with ethical tensions around balancing protection and agency, particularly when working with vulnerable populations.

Rogers et al. (2016) exemplify this approach through a participatory action research project with young children, exploring how to balance ethical protection with the authentic expression of student voice. Their work highlights the importance of ongoing assent, child-centred methods, and the ethical imperative to avoid silencing under the guise of safeguarding.

Photovoice methodologies, as used by Mannion et al. (2024) and Busher (2022), offer visual and narrative tools that reposition students -particularly those with intellectual disabilities or from marginalized backgrounds- as co-researchers. These approaches emphasize ethical inclusion, accessibility, and the co-construction of meaning, aligning with Lundy's (2017) model of participation (space, voice, audience, influence).

Gavilanes (2022) and O'Neill (2018) extend the ethical discourse by interrogating the limits of representation and advocating for non-extractive, relational ethics. Gavilanes proposes *ethics of refusal* to protect migrant and refugee students from the objectifying gaze of traditional research, while O'Neill argues for a child-centric ethics that recognizes children as competent social agents.

In more institutional contexts, Finefter-Rosenbluh (2022) explores how student voice is mediated through feedback systems and assessment reforms. This study reveals the ethical tensions between empowering student expression and protecting teacher well-being, raising questions about surveillance, performativity, and the commodification of voice.

Across these diverse studies, ethics is not treated as a procedural add-on but as a foundational concern that shapes every aspect of student voice research: from design and data collection to interpretation and dissemination. The ethical imperative is clear: to engage with students not merely as subjects of research but as co-constructors of knowledge, whose voices matter in both educational practice and policy. Indeed, these studies collectively advocate for context-sensitive consent protocols, critical reflexivity, and methodological flexibility to uphold children's rights while mitigating risks of harm.

Practitioner Inquiry or Practitioner Research refers to systematic, reflective investigations conducted by educators into their own practices with the aim of improving

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teaching and learning. It is grounded in professional experience and emphasizes intellectual autonomy, ethical reflection, and collaborative learning.

Looking at its characteristics, practitioner research or inquiry is:

- Conducted by educators within their own institutions
- Focuses on real instructional or administrative challenges
- Encourages structured reflection and methodological rigor
- Often linked to professional development

This form of inquiry is grounded in the belief that practitioners possess unique, context-rich knowledge and are well-positioned to generate meaningful insights through systematic reflection and action. The reviewed literature (e.g., Banegas & Consoli, 2025; Gharaveisi & Dastgoshadeh, 2020; Stevens et al., 2016) reveals six articles in which ethics is not peripheral but central to practitioner research, shaping both the process and the relationships it entails.

Gibbs and Costley (2006) argue that practitioner researchers, as insiders, must navigate complex ethical terrains due to their dual roles. They advocate for an “ethics of care” that emphasizes relational responsibility, trust, and attentiveness to the moral dimensions of everyday professional interactions. This perspective is echoed by Stevens et al. (2016), who propose Structured Ethical Reflection (SER) as a tool to help practitioner researchers articulate and embody their core values throughout the research process. Banegas and Consoli (2025) further highlight the ethical tensions that arise when academic researchers collaborate with practitioners. Their duo-ethnographic reflection reveals concerns about transparency, co-option, and the need to disrupt hierarchical knowledge production.

In more applied contexts, Alasiry (2019) demonstrates how practitioner research can support inclusive education. As a teacher in a school for deaf students, she uses participatory action research to co-construct knowledge with students and staff. Her work underscores the ethical imperative of ensuring meaningful participation and respecting the agency of marginalized learners. Edwards-Groves and Davidson (2020) also illustrate how practitioner inquiry can enhance dialogic pedagogy. Their study, conducted in twelve classrooms, shows how teachers’ reflective engagement with student interaction fosters ethical awareness and pedagogical responsiveness.

Through these studies, ethicality is framed as iterative and dialogic, requiring continuous negotiation rather than compliance with static rules. Ethics in practitioner research is portrayed as relational, situated, and ongoing. It involves more than compliance with institutional review boards; it requires a commitment to reflexivity, mutual respect, and the co-construction of knowledge. Practitioner researchers are called not only to

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improve practice but to do so in ways that are ethically grounded, socially just, and contextually responsive.

Autoethnography or **Personal Narrative** combines autobiography and ethnography, allowing researchers to explore cultural phenomena through personal experience and self-reflection. It challenges traditional notions of objectivity by positioning the researcher as both subject and observer. Indeed, they have gained prominence in educational research for their capacity to bridge the personal and professional, the subjective and the scholarly. In this methodological approach, ethics play a central and multifaceted role, as evidenced by the studies reviewed.

Autoethnography or personal narrative:

- Centres on the researcher's lived experience
- Connects personal stories to broader cultural contexts
- Uses narrative, diary, and reflective writing
- Emphasizes emotional and ethical dimensions

These approaches centre the researcher's lived experience as both the site and source of inquiry, offering a powerful means to interrogate identity, practice, and ethics from within, as the five articles revised suggest (e.g., Díaz, 2023; Poulton, 2023). Díaz's (2023) narrative reveals how personal, academic, and professional identities intersect in the field, and how ethical tensions emerge from these entanglements. Through reflective storytelling, she challenges conventional notions of objectivity and advocates for a situated, relational ethics grounded in transparency and responsiveness.

Gavilanes (2022) extends this ethical reflection through a decolonial lens. Her work critiques extractive research practices and proposes **ethics of refusal** as a methodological stance. By choosing not to collect data that could reify harm, she repositions ethical responsibility as a refusal to exploit vulnerable populations. Her narrative underscores the importance of epistemic humility and the need to reimagine research as a space of solidarity rather than surveillance.

Poulton (2023), on the other hand, drawing on vignettes from his experience as an insider teacher-researcher, illustrates how ethical decision-making is shaped by character traits such as integrity, courage, and empathy. His work highlights the moral complexity of conducting research in familiar settings and the value of reflective practice in navigating these challenges. Hopman (2021) contributes to this discourse through narrative inquiry embedded in action research. Her use of fieldwork supervision as a tool for ethical reflexivity reveals how emotional awareness and relational dynamics shape the research process. By acknowledging the affective dimensions of inquiry, she deepens both the analytical and ethical rigor of her work.

Alan (2019) presents a narrative self-study that foregrounds the researcher's dual role as subject and investigator. Through personal experience methods, he examines his

teaching practices from the perspectives of students and colleagues. His study emphasizes the transformative potential of self-inquiry and the ethical imperative of authenticity, vulnerability, and dialogic engagement in educational research.

Together, these studies demonstrate that autoethnography and personal narrative are not merely methodological choices but ethical commitments. They require researchers to engage deeply with their own positionality, to remain accountable to the communities they study, and to embrace the vulnerability inherent in telling one's own story. In doing so, they contribute to a more humane, reflective, and ethically grounded research practice.

(Classroom) Case Study research provides a powerful methodological framework for exploring complex, situated phenomena within real-world classroom and institutional contexts. They enable deep, situated inquiry while foregrounding the ethical responsibilities of researchers who are embedded in the communities they study. These studies show that ethics is not an external constraint but an integral part of designing, conducting, and interpreting meaningful educational research.

Its main characteristics are:

- Offers contextual depth and situated inquiry
- Provides reflexivity and insider perspective
- Focuses on pedagogical transformation
- Uses methodological pluralism

The three studies reviewed here (e.g., Serra et al., 2023; Edwards-Groves & Davidson, 2020; Makar et al., 2024) demonstrate how case study approaches, whether ethnographic, reflexive, or practitioner-based, can illuminate the ethical, cultural, and pedagogical dimensions of teaching and learning.

Makar et al. (2024) employ a classroom-based case study through an interdisciplinary approach, integrating data science, computational thinking, and ethical reasoning. The study highlights how ethical considerations—such as data privacy and age-appropriate inquiry—are embedded in both the design and facilitation of learning experiences. The case study method allows for a detailed, context-sensitive analysis of student engagement and the ethical scaffolding required to support it.

Nikkanen (2019) offers a reflexive ethnographic case study grounded in her personal experience as an ethnic minority student in a university setting. Her narrative reveals the subtle dynamics of exclusion and voice within group work, challenging assumptions of neutrality in academic collaboration. The case study format enables a deep exploration of identity, power, and positionality, while also foregrounding the ethical imperative of acknowledging and addressing systemic bias in educational spaces.

Whereas Douglas et al. (2020) contribute to a classroom-based practitioner inquiry, reframing *difficult knowledge* not as a barrier but as an opportunity for ethical and relational pedagogy. Through case-based reflection, they explore how students and teachers navigate the tensions of settler-colonial histories and cultural disruption. The ethical dimension of their work lies in its commitment to honouring Indigenous knowledge systems and fostering dialogic, inclusive learning environments.

In these studies, ethics is not treated as a procedural add-on but as a foundational element of case study research. Whether through the protection of student data, the interrogation of cultural identity, or the respectful engagement with Indigenous epistemologies, ethics shapes the questions asked, the methods employed, and the interpretations drawn. Case study research, when conducted reflexively and relationally, becomes a vehicle for ethical inquiry—one that is attuned to the lived realities of learners and educators alike.

4.2. Delimiting the Contexts of Teacher-Researcher Action

In terms of contexts of action, research carried out by teachers often extends beyond the classroom, engaging with families, communities, and broader sociopolitical issues, thereby blurring the boundaries between teaching, research, and activism. The reviewed articles, however, focus on three research contexts, as seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Number of articles per research context emerged. Source: own elaboration

Classroom Context refers to research conducted within the boundaries of a teaching session, typically involving direct interaction with students. It often focuses on instructional strategies, student engagement, learning outcomes, and teacher-student dynamics. This context is central to understanding pedagogical practices and their impact on learners. Based on the literature reviewed (e.g., Alan, 2019; Edwards-Groves & Davidson, 2020; Finefter-Rosenbluh, 2022; Rogers et al., 2016; Serra et al., 2023; Stapleton et al., 2017), 14 studies were conducted in this context.

Looking at the themes of these studies, the most common ones are:

- Implementation of innovative teaching strategies (e.g., dialogic pedagogy, student-led tutorials)
- Ethical considerations in working with minors (e.g. student vulnerability, privacy, and power dynamics)
- Inclusion and student voice in classroom decision-making
- Integration of interdisciplinary content (e.g., science and art, data science)
- Teacher-researcher roles and reflective practice

When exploring the research methodologies used, several studies adopt PAR frameworks to engage students as co-constructors of knowledge within their learning environments. For instance, Rogers et al. (2016) conducted a year-long action research project in a kindergarten classroom in the United States, using read-aloud sessions of social justice-themed literature to explore children's responses to issues of inequality. The study foregrounds ethical tensions between protection and voice, advocating for participant-centred techniques and ongoing assent as ethical imperatives when working with young children.

In Australia, Makar et al. (2024) examined how primary students (aged 9–10) addressed complex problems using non-standard data in a data science framework. The classroom-based case study highlighted the importance of introducing ethical issues - such as data privacy and digital responsibility- in age-appropriate ways, integrating them into the inquiry-based learning process.

A second cluster of studies centres on the role of the teacher-researcher and the reflexive dimensions of insider research. Díaz (2023), through an autoethnographic account of her fieldwork in a Mexican primary school, reflects on the shifting interplay between her roles as researcher, postgraduate student, and teacher educator. The study underscores the ethical complexity of positionality and the need for adaptive strategies in response to field-based dilemmas.

Poulton (2023) offers a virtues-based ethical framework for navigating insider research in the UK, drawing on personal vignettes to illustrate how character dispositions influence ethical decision-making. Similarly, Hopman (2021) explores the use of fieldwork supervision as a tool for ethical reflexivity in an Australian action research project, emphasizing the emotional and relational dimensions of research ethics.

A third thematic strand focuses on the inclusion of student voices, particularly those of marginalized or vulnerable learners. Douglas et al. (2020) document how students in Canadian K–12 classrooms engaged with Indigenous perspectives not as **difficult knowledge** but as opportunities for relational renegotiation. The study, grounded in practitioner inquiry, highlights the ethical imperative of disrupting settler-colonial narratives through pedagogical interventions.

Faldet and Nes (2024) in Norway, and Mannion et al. (2024) in Ireland, both explore participatory methodologies that amplify the voices of students with special educational needs. The former emphasizes the ethical necessity of listening to vulnerable children in ways that are contextually sensitive and justifiable, while the latter employs the Photovoice method to reposition students with intellectual disabilities as co-researchers. Both studies operationalize ethical participation through frameworks such as Lundy's (2007) model of participation.

Finally, several studies examine the dynamics of collaboration between teachers and external researchers. Bergmark et al. (2024) investigate mentoring roles in action research in Sweden, using Noddings' (1984, 1992) ethics of care to conceptualize mentoring as a relational and situated practice. The study proposes four metaphors -the gardener, the shepherd, the teacher, and the bridge-builder- to illustrate the fluidity and ethical sensitivity required in mentoring relationships.

Mueller et al. (2023) reflect on a four-year action research collaboration in Canadian bilingual programmes, where teachers and researchers co-designed and implemented pedagogical strategies to enhance oral language use. Ethical challenges emerged around communication, time constraints, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, necessitating ongoing negotiation of roles and responsibilities.

Across these diverse studies, ethics is not treated as a procedural formality but as a situated, relational, and often transformative practice. Common ethical themes included in the studies are:

- Informed and ongoing consent, particularly with young or vulnerable participants.
- Protection of identity and privacy, especially in digital or sensitive contexts.
- Negotiation of power and positionality, in both teacher-student and researcher-participant relationships.
- Recognition of student agency, through participatory and inclusive methodologies.
- Reflexivity and care as guiding principles in navigating ethical dilemmas.

These studies collectively challenge minimalist interpretations of research ethics, advocating instead for a dynamic and context-responsive ethical stance that aligns with the values of educational justice, inclusion, and professional integrity.

School-based Research occupies a unique position in educational inquiry, as it is embedded within the everyday realities of teaching and learning. 13 studies were identified in this review (e.g., Areljung et al., 2021; Bergmark, 2020; Banegas & Consoli, 2024; Clough & Tarr, 2021), which reflect a PAR approach and a philosophical inquiry and inclusive pedagogies, each situated within the institutional, cultural, and ethical complexities of school environments.

Studies reviewed highlight ethical challenges in collaborative practitioner research, particularly regarding role negotiation, ownership of data, and institutional constraints (e.g. Andrew, 2017; Busher, 2022; Gharaveisi & Dastgoshadeh, 2020). Ethical strategies include structured ethical reflection, care ethics frameworks, and shared governance models to balance researcher and practitioner interests while safeguarding participants (e.g. Bakerson, et al., 2015; Niemi, 2019; Nikkanen, 2019; Stevens et al., 2016).

One prominent strand of school-based research focuses on inclusive education and the amplification of student voice. For example, Alasiry (2019) explores the use of PAR in a Saudi Arabian school for deaf students. The study positions students not merely as subjects but as active participants in shaping inclusive practices. Ethical considerations are central, particularly in ensuring that students with disabilities are not only heard but meaningfully involved in the research process. The study highlights the importance of dialogical ethics, where inclusion is both a pedagogical and moral imperative.

In a different yet complementary vein, Quiroga and Cortés (2024) engage in a philosophical and autoethnographic exploration of research in childhood and education. Conducted within a Mexican public primary school, the study reflects on the researcher's multiple identities -as educator, postgraduate student, and fieldworker- and how these intersect with the school context. The narrative foregrounds the ethical tensions that arise when the researcher is both insider and outsider, and how these tensions shape the production of knowledge. Ethics here is not procedural but relational and situated, requiring constant negotiation of roles, responsibilities, and power dynamics.

Across these studies, ethics emerge not as a static checklist but as a dynamic, context-sensitive practice. Several key themes recur:

- Relational ethics: Emphasizing care, trust, and mutual respect between researchers and participants.
- Positionality and reflexivity: Acknowledging the researcher's embeddedness in the school context and the implications for power and representation.
- Inclusive participation: Ensuring that all voices, particularly those of marginalized students, are not only heard but actively shape the research process.
- Transformative intent: Viewing research as a vehicle for social and educational change within the school.

These ethical dimensions are particularly salient in school-based contexts, where the boundaries between research and practice are often blurred, and where the stakes -both personal and institutional- are high.

Community-based Research represents a paradigm shift from research on communities to research with communities. It emphasizes collaboration, mutual learning, and social transformation; however, sometimes it includes school-based and classroom-based contexts, too. The 12 studies identified in this review (e.g., Bourke et

al., 2017; Faldet & Nes, 2024; Gavilanes, 2022; Mitra & McCormick, 2017; O'Neill, 2018; Seehawer, 2018; Serpa Perdomo, 2024) reflect this ethos, offering insights into how educational research can be grounded in community realities while navigating complex ethical terrains. The main themes emerged in these studies are:

- Community-engaged scholarship: collaborative research between universities and local communities, especially around school closures and social justice.
- Grassroots activism: documentation of community organizing efforts and participatory needs assessments.
- Decolonial and Indigenous perspectives: research grounded in Ubuntu ethics and relational ontologies.
- Inclusive practices: community-led initiatives to support marginalized groups, including refugee and migrant students.
- Horizontal dialogue mechanisms: to ensure inclusivity and relational accountability.

A central theme across several studies is the use of PAR to engage communities in identifying and addressing their own educational needs. For instance, Wagle et al. (2023) document a school-based needs assessment in rural Nepal, where community members, teachers, and researchers collaboratively explored educational challenges. The study highlights the emergence of relational ontologies, where knowledge is co-constructed through dialogue and mutual respect. Ethical considerations are foregrounded through the emphasis on informed consent, epistemic justice, and the politics of participation.

Similarly, Burroughs (2018) explores ethics education in early childhood settings, conceptualizing schools as sociomoral environments. While not exclusively community-based, the study underscores the importance of ethical pluralism and collaborative partnerships between educators, families, and communities in shaping children's moral development.

Agard et al. (2019) offer a critical reflection on Community-Engaged Scholarship (CES) in the context of school closures in the United States. The study presents three models of engagement -participatory action research, engaged documentation, and grassroots listening- each with varying degrees of collaboration between researchers and community members. The authors highlight the ethical tensions inherent in CES, including issues of power asymmetry, voice and representation, and the ownership of knowledge. Rather than offering a prescriptive model, the study advocates for a context-sensitive ethics that is responsive to the lived realities of marginalized communities.

In a more conceptual contribution, Gibbs and Costley (2006) propose an ethics of care for practitioner researchers working within their own communities or organizations. Drawing on examples from professional doctorates, the authors argue that traditional rule-based ethics are insufficient for capturing the moral complexity of insider research.

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Instead, they advocate for a relational and situated ethics, where researchers are attuned to the interpersonal dynamics and emotional labour involved in community-based inquiry.

Tan (2017) explores cross-disciplinary creativity and design thinking through an action research project involving a community of practice. While the study is situated within a broader educational innovation framework, it emphasizes the humanistic values of design thinking -such as respect, dialogue, and complementarity- as ethical foundations for community-based educational transformation.

In these studies, ethics is not merely a procedural requirement, but a praxis of engagement. Several key ethical dimensions emerge:

- **Co-construction of knowledge:** communities are not passive subjects but active co-researchers.
- **Relational accountability:** ethical responsibility is grounded in relationships, not just regulations.
- **Contextual sensitivity:** ethical decisions are shaped by local histories, power dynamics, and cultural norms.
- **Transformative intent:** research is oriented toward social justice, empowerment, and systemic change.

These principles challenge conventional notions of objectivity and neutrality, positioning ethics as a dynamic, dialogic, and deeply human dimension of community-based educational research.

5. Conclusions and future directions

This context mapping report offers a significant contribution to the understanding of ethical competence in teacher-led educational research. It highlights the growing recognition of teachers as practitioner-researchers who engage in systematic inquiry to inform and transform their practice. The scoping review points out that ethical competence is not merely a procedural requirement but a foundational, relational, and context-sensitive dimension of the teacher-researcher identity.

Key findings reveal that ethical practices are deeply embedded across all stages of the research cycle -from design to dissemination- and are particularly salient in methodologies such as (Participatory) Action Research, Student Voice Research, and Autoethnography. These approaches foreground the importance of informed consent, reflexivity, power negotiation, and the inclusion of marginalized voices. The report also emphasizes the transformative potential of ethically grounded research to foster professional growth, institutional change, and educational justice.

The review also identifies notable limitations in the existing literature. Despite the increasing emphasis on ethics in educational research, there remains a lack of empirical studies that explicitly address the development of ethical competence in teacher-researchers. This highlights the need to embed ethics research competence within teacher initial education programmes. Furthermore, literature often treats ethics as an implicit or secondary concern, rather than as a central component of research training.

There is also a scarcity of frameworks that support teachers in navigating the ethical dilemmas that arise from their dual role as educators and researchers, particularly in contexts lacking formal ethics oversight.

Moreover, the report identifies critical areas for further development, particularly in the cultivation of ethical competence as a core dimension of teacher professionalism. There is a pressing need to move beyond compliance-based models of ethics toward more situated, dialogic, and transformative approaches. This includes fostering teachers' capacity to engage in structured ethical reflection, to recognize and respond to power dynamics in research relationships, and to make contextually sensitive decisions that uphold the dignity and rights of all participants.

Future research and professional development efforts should prioritize the integration of ethics education into teacher training and continuous professional learning. This entails designing learning experiences that enable teachers to engage with real-world ethical dilemmas through case-based reasoning, collaborative inquiry, and reflective practice. Specifically, the scoping review underscores that there are some key ethical dilemmas faced by teachers-researchers:

1. Role conflict and positionality

- Teachers must navigate the tension between their responsibilities as educators and their roles as researchers. This includes managing boundaries, avoiding role confusion, and being transparent about their dual identity.
 - Ethical dilemmas emerge when teachers access sensitive information by virtue of their teaching role, raising questions about consent, confidentiality, and the appropriate use of such data.
2. Power dynamics
- The inherent power imbalance between teachers and students complicates issues of voluntary participation and informed consent.
 - Teachers must ensure that students (especially minors or vulnerable groups) feel genuinely free to participate or withdraw without fear of repercussions.
3. Informed and ongoing consent
- Obtaining consent is not a one-time event but a continuous process. Teachers must adapt consent procedures to the age, cognitive development, and cultural background of participants.
 - Ethical tensions arise when students' understanding of the research evolves or when their circumstances change during the study.
4. Confidentiality and data protection
- Teachers often collect data in familiar settings where anonymity is difficult to guarantee. They must balance transparency with the need to protect identities, especially in small or close-knit school communities.
 - Managing sensitive disclosures (e.g., related to abuse, discrimination, or mental health) requires careful ethical judgment and may involve conflicting duties of care and confidentiality.
5. Representation and voice
- Teachers must avoid misrepresenting or stereotyping participants, particularly marginalized or underrepresented groups.
 - Ethical dilemmas occur when deciding how to include student voices authentically without tokenism or exploitation.
6. Insider research and bias

- As insiders, teacher-researchers may struggle with objectivity, over-identification, or blind spots. Their proximity to the research context can both enrich and complicate ethical decision-making.
- Reflexivity is essential to acknowledge and mitigate personal biases and assumptions.

7. Equity and inclusion

- Ensuring that all students have equitable opportunities to participate in research is a persistent ethical challenge, especially when working with students with disabilities, language barriers, or socio-economic disadvantages.

8. Emotional and relational complexity

- Research often involves emotional labour, especially when dealing with sensitive topics or vulnerable populations. Teachers must manage their own emotional responses while maintaining ethical integrity.

9. Dissemination and publication of findings

- Teachers face dilemmas about how to share findings responsibly, ensuring that dissemination benefits the community and does not cause harm or misinterpretation.
- Issues of authorship, recognition, and returning results to participants are also ethically significant.

The development of digital tools and simulations, as envisioned by the TEACHer project, offers promising avenues for supporting self-directed learning and ethical decision-making in diverse educational contexts.

This report advocates for the institutionalisation of ethical competence as a lifelong learning goal for educators. This includes creating spaces for peer mentoring, professional dialogue, and community-based research that reinforce ethical awareness and collective responsibility, such as (online) Communities of Practice. By embedding ethics into the fabric of teacher-researcher identity, educators can be empowered not only to conduct research responsibly but to act as agents of ethical and educational transformation.

In conclusion, the findings of this report call for a renewed commitment to the ethical dimension of teacher research. Supporting teachers in developing ethical competence through authentic, contextually grounded, and participatory approaches is essential to

advancing both the quality and integrity of educational research and the professionalization of teaching.

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